

The Mediating Effect of Job Security on Career Management Practices and Administrative Staff Job Satisfaction in Chartered Public Universities in Kenya

Josephine Jepkorir Inyangala¹ Prof. Fred.K. Keraro²

Faculty of Commerce Faculty of Education and Community Studies
Egerton University, Kenya

Dr. Simon Kipchumba³

Faculty of Commerce
Egerton University, Kenya

ABSTRACT

The study sought to establish the mediating effect of job security on career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction in chartered public universities in Kenya. The study adopted correlational survey research design. The target population comprised 2,355 administrative staff in chartered public universities in Kenya. Purposive sampling technique was used to select ten (10) fully-fledged chartered public universities. Proportionate random sampling technique was used to select 370 administrative staff. Data was collected using three questionnaires, namely; University Administrative Staff Questionnaires (UASQ). The questionnaires were pilot tested to ascertain its content, construct and face validity before use. Reliability of instruments was estimated using Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient for internal consistency. Reliability coefficient of 0.944 was yielded. Data was analyzed with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics were used to describe the profile of respondents and study variables. Multiple regressions were used to test hypotheses at a significance level of alpha (α) equal to 0.05. The findings indicate that, job security partially mediate the relationship between career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction. Further, the study demonstrated the effect of job security and this provides new insights on the role of job security in enhancing job satisfaction. It is recommended that chartered public universities to embrace job security and integrate with career management practices and human resource functions to enhance job satisfaction.

Key Words: Job Security, Career management practice, Administrative Staff Job Satisfaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Job security is a work-related stressor linked with employees' job satisfaction, commitment and performance (Artz & Keya, 2015). Sender, Arnold and Staffelbach (2017) state that employees perceive job security to be the risk of job loss in the near future. In terms of organization, job security is defined in relation to employee personality differential; that is, the self-esteem regarding the likelihood of remaining relevant on the job and the ability to manage and handle information in a positive way (emotional intelligence) and the behavioral satisfaction (Ma, Liu & Wang, 2016). Greenhalh and Rosenblatt conceptualized the idea of employee job security in (1984). Distinguished between the thoughts and fear associated with one's job loss due to technological changes in the globe. However, Huang, Lee, Ashford and Chen (2010) illustrated this by the results of two meta-analyses on employee self-esteem and emotional intelligence. The meta-results correlate with employee overall job satisfaction. The study concludes that, employee with higher level of emotional intelligence has the ability to manage information accurately and limit the negative consequences associated with job security. Sander and Erling (2012) found similar attributes in their study on the role of emotions in customer and employees complaint behaviour. The observation from the study indicates that, employee overall satisfaction was significant and positive, relates with employee behaviour of coming to work, keeping time, positive thinking, pleasant, willingness to do extra work and job satisfaction. Ma, Liu and Wang (2016) suggests that, employee job security is a method an institution could use to communicate with employees that the institution values and needs their labour and contribution mediates their relationship. Therefore, career management practices is linked

with job security and in turn affects employees' job satisfaction and organizational outcome. Komendat and Didona (2016) state that, organization that engage employee's fully on career management practices fosters an environment of job security, exerts a positive impact on job satisfaction.

Therefore, Career Management Practices (CMP) are organizational human resource functions concerned with the provision of opportunities for employees to develop their abilities and their careers in order to ensure that the organization has the flow of talent that it needs and to satisfy employees aspirations (McEloy & Wang, 2016). Baruch and Peiperl (2000) identified seventeen CMPs which include; recruitment, compensation, reward, mentoring, promotion, retirement programmes just to mention a few, though four major components are considered the most important activities in CMP. First component are career needs, which include; career goal needs, career task needs and career challenge. Career needs influence job positions and responsibilities, though they vary a lot in terms of employee stage of career and level of hierarchy (Tser, pao, & Ching, 2010). The second component is Career Panning Initiatives (CPI) that outline the structure, framework and approaches on different aspects of career information, career counseling, career self-assessment and job rotation (Walia & Bajaj, 2012). The third component is Career Development Programmes (CDP) that identify skill gaps and developmental activities that provide employees' with flexible opportunity within the system to continually take part in more advanced training. The fourth and last component is Career Path Progression (CPP), a visible competency profile against which employees can map their own career progress and aspirations. This can either be a linear, multiple or boundary less path (Cao & Thomas, 2013). Armstrong (2009) similarly explained that, CMPs ensure that the institution has the flow of talents it needs. Shibly (2011) conceptualized it as a function that ensures proper Human Resource Information System (HRIS), structure, policy and procedures that guide the organization and employees to analyze and organize information on career, hence influences job satisfaction.

Higher education institutions in Africa have challenges on CMP as compared to the western countries, because many of them have not embraced the use of technology to manage HR functions (Okurame, 2009). The challenge has led to prescribed constraints on the CMP and employees' job specifications. The constraints have affected certain category of staff, the administrator staff. Career development for such category of employees involves attending specific training, seminars, workshops and conference, which offer opportunities to learn new skills, network and share knowledge (Osibanjo, Oyewunmi & Ojo, 2014). Such practices enable them to progress, advance, improve skills and knowledge and may hold high job positions and responsibilities that may act as job security and hence influence job satisfaction. In contrast, when the opportunities are absent or unknown by the employee may lead to stagnated career growth and job dissatisfaction. Idowu (2012) examined the relationship between organizational career management, development practices and job satisfaction of support staff in selected university libraries in Southwest Nigeria. The results indicate a positive linear relationship between organizational career management and job satisfaction. The study demonstrate the effectiveness of implementing career management and career development practices that have a major impact on job satisfaction, influence employee attitude and job security.

In Kenya, more High Education Institutions (HEIs), both public and private have been established to meet the growing demand for higher education. Student enrolment has also grown, making it necessary for them to employ more staff, and in particular administrative staff. Administrative staffs are under the category of non-teaching staff. This cadre of administrative staff includes, Administrative Assistant, Senior Administrative Assistant, Assistant Registrar and Registrar. They hold a bachelor degree and above. They are deployed to serve in key functional sections, departments of the university both in academic and in non-academic. Their work is to over administrative duties as per the university strategic plan and oversee the implementation of HR functions. The primary task of implementing and executing the strategy successfully depends partly on institutions' human resource, to have significant effect on employee job satisfaction and performance (Shikanga, 2009). However, public universities are operating in a very competitive global environment; competent work force create competitive edge for survival and for business excellence. This can be achieved through a thorough understanding of employees' job satisfaction. Luo (2012), Kibet and Wanyama (2001) studies on job satisfaction and performance found that, administrative staffs in institutions were cause of concern because of increased job dissatisfaction on specific work-related aspects of the job. The studies suggested empirical observation on their lesser happiness in relation with their remuneration, rigid promotion criteria, nature of work, relationship with both supervisor and co-worker and job security. Thus challenging the institutional goal to attract and retain talent, yet studies have found job aspects play a significant role in enhancing employees' job satisfaction (Lumley, Coetzee, Tladinyane, & Ferreira, 2011; Chen, Ployhart, Thomas, Anderson & Bliese, 2011).

II. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Employees are widely recognized as the most important source of sustainable competitive advantage and a measure of an organization's attempt to stay ahead. The ability to attract and retain employees become increasingly important as does the pursuit of CMP that enable employees to advance and enhance employee's job security and job satisfaction. However, human resource information system, the structure and the policies that provide the basis for effective CMP are held in low esteem in chartered public universities in Kenya. The information that supports CMP is a challenge, reflection of unclear identification of employee's career needs, career planning, career development and career progression. That would enable the chartered public universities effectively implement CMP. Arguably, this may have led to stagnated career growth and career progression. In turn, affect pay, nature of work and relationship with both supervisor and co-worker. Hence, influence employee achievement especially for the administrative staff leading to job dissatisfaction. These cadres of employee's have devise ways to quantify their job security and job satisfaction, and inadequate tapping of in-house talent, skills, knowledge and abilities challenge the goal to attract and retain talents. The discrepancy leave administrative staff holding low esteem and negative attitudes towards their jobs hence influence job security and job dissatisfaction. Studies have examined the influence of CMP on performance and few have examined the mediating effect of job security on CMP and job satisfaction. Thus, this study therefore, sought to empirically examine and explore the mediating effect of job security on CMP and administrative staff job satisfaction in chartered public universities in Kenya.

III. PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

This study examined relationship between selected CMP and administrative staff job satisfaction, and job security as a mediating factor in chartered public universities, Kenya. The study attempted to empirically examine and explore the inter-correlations among the variables.

IV. OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

To establish the mediating effect of job security on career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction in chartered public universities in Kenya.

V. RESEARCH HYPOTHESIS

Job security has no statistically significant effect on career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction in chartered public universities in Kenya.

VI. LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of job security started with the works of Greenhalgh and Rosenblatt (1984) in which they conceptualized antecedents and consequences of job security and insecurity. Akpan (2013) stated that job security relates to employee outcome such as job satisfaction. Akpan ideas, though and suggestion on job security regard to holding and losing one's job and the feeling and fear associated with it, was due to global technical changes that led to restructuring downsizing and mergers. Witte and Sverke (2013) stated that, such technologies force employees to change mindset, acquire the right skills, and adapt to change, has brought anxiety on the way they perceive their jobs. Employees perceive themselves to be powerless in their expectations of future job continuity. De Witte (2005) argued that, job security is a perception expectation about continuity in a current job situation. Jeanne and Melinda, (2015) suggests strategies that may serve as an intervention in the management of the negative outcome of perceived job insecurity, can be broadly defined as personality differential which includes; self-esteem, emotional intelligence and behavioural satisfaction.

6.1 Personality Differential

The concept of perceived personality differential is self-esteem and emotional intelligence. These concepts are considered as the most important aspect reflected in job security as shown to be detrimental for various types of employees (Sender, Arnold, & Staffelbach, 2017). While empirical studies shows that, the detrimental outcome of this workplace phenomena affect the individual employee self-esteem and emotions, at the same time it is being associated with the organizational outcome (Kolawole, Ajani & Adisa, 2013). However, most findings have focused on the organizational outcome of this phenomenon without giving a proper attention to its outcome in the larger employee outcome. When an employee feels their job security is threatened their self-esteem go down due to reduction in the rate of job openings. They find other opportunities yet organizations are in competition and the effect it has on job satisfaction (Zhang, 2014). Empirical studies shows that, one of the most important and powerful job characteristic in determining job satisfaction is job security (Kamendet & Didona, 2016). De Witte (2013) illustrated by the results of two meta-analyses on employee self-esteem and emotional intelligence; in which the meta-results correlate with employee job satisfaction.

6.2 Employee Self-esteem

De Witte (2013) attempted to study job security in a deeper level, arguing that job security was multi-dimensional and incorporated self-esteem, emerging from threat appraisal, and reaction regarding the likelihood of remaining relevant on the job. Kinnunen, Feldt and Mauno (2003). Study on job security and employee self-esteem using exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis in South African context indicated that self-esteem has a two-dimensional constructs, attitudinal and health related outcomes. The study indicated that the two factors correlate with employee job satisfaction. However, Munnell and Fraenkel (2013) argue that, employee low social status and low self-worth belief can indulge an individual to have a negative self-concept, lower self-esteem, and a pessimistic attitude towards life perceive job loss. However, an individual who perceive a high self-esteem will have a higher future endeavors, they would feel less threatened by the belief of future job loss and thus, they react less to negative consequences that are associated with it. Therefore, organizations' engage in various adaptive strategies in order to tackle the new demands and remain vigorous in unpredictable environment effect. Although reorganization strategies differ in many ways, but they usually have at least one thing in common, that is, transformation of employees working life and motivating employees' to lessen the perception of job loss.

6.3 Employee Emotional Intelligence

Jordan, Ashkanasy & Hartel (2002) defined emotional intelligence as, the ability to identify, use, understand, and manage emotions in a positive way. It also includes communicating effectively, empathizing with others, overcoming challenges, and defusing conflict. Empirical research show that employees with emotional intelligence show greater self-awareness, self-management, social awareness and positive relationship with organization management. In addition, they have greater mental health, exemplary job performance, and have leadership skills. Hence, an employee with higher level of emotional intelligence serve as a coping strategy, help an individual to limit the negative consequences associated with job security. For instance, anxiety, depression, negative self-concepts associated with perceived job security can be easily taken care of if an individual with emotional intelligence (Zhao, Wayne, Glibkowski & Bravo, (2007). Similarly, the higher the need for security in an individual, the more likely he is to react to the negative consequences of perceived job security. The belief of such an individual is properly more on the social, material and status and he/she may react less to threatening job position or job conditions (Borg & Elizur, 1992).

Employees' with high level of emotional intelligence will therefore, invest more in their institutions out of loyalty or because they view their jobs as long-term commitment. On the other hand, employees' may take advantage of job security to advance in their careers (Burke, 1991). Neal (2004) stated that, job security is an important determinant of employee health, physical and psychological wellbeing, employee turnover, employee retention, and employee job satisfaction. Hence, institution needs to pay more attention to the effect of job security when making decisions regarding improving the level of job satisfaction of their employees' in order to improve job satisfaction and performance.

6.4 Behavioural Satisfaction

According to Yi-Wei and Polonsky (2012), behavioural satisfaction focuses on employee intentions in work environment such as commitment and loyalty towards the organization. Morrison (2008) argue that employee behaviour is more or less driven by attitudes and attitudes are salient but reflect one's behaviour; found that employee overall satisfaction have significant relationship between employee behaviour of coming to work, keeping time, positive thinking, pleasant, willingness to do extra work and job satisfaction. Wilson and Dunn (1986) states that, employees' behaviour they engage in for their own seek are likely to be affective; on the other hand, behaviour intended to accompany a goal are likely to be cognitive and are tied to the work functions, policy, procedures and organizational structure. However, may determine how employees feel, think, motivate themselves and behave. Sander and Erling (2012) found that persons dispositional high in self-awareness exhibit higher behavioural correlations than do persons low in self-awareness. Therefore, job security is a function of cognitive, that reflects one's belief and confident in capability, a strong sense of efficacy that enhance accomplishment in certain task and a feeling of calmness the employees experience about in relation to their career (affective) in turn impact on the behaviour either positive or negative in the work environment.

VII. Career Management in Organizations

Hall and Bola (2010) express similar views on career as an individual perceived sequence of attitudes and behaviours associated with work-related experiences and activities of a person's life. The concept started during the industrial revolution. At that time, the world experienced economic growth and demand for human capital. Employees had an abundance of job opportunities and mutual loyalty between the employer and employees. Career was viewed as being relatively stable with a linear progression (Hall, 1996). The rule was, take the job and respect the employer, keep your nose to the grindstone and your mouth shut. Employees' enjoyed regular promotions, which allowed for upward

advancement within an organization, and retirement with a pension (Hall & Moss, 1998). Since then, changes in the global market have altered the sequence. Chiaburu, Baker and Pitariu (2006) noted that there were so many changes in the environment that needed to be revisited. So much job insecurity in terms of career, career options and modifications of career path progression were needed to secure employees cognitive feeling. There was also need for an appropriate career plan structure, as an essential input for career management. Employees needed support to develop skills, knowledge, competence and value to execute their work (Baruch & Peiperl, 2000). CMP hence become the nexus between organizations and individual employees.

The change informed organizations that they are no longer the sole owner of career system. That awareness led to matching of employees' interest and capabilities, organizational goals and career opportunities. Through planned programmes that encompasses activities such as career planning, career development and career pathways, initiated by organizational HRM. Chen, Chang and Yeh (2004) offered a much richer perspective of the options and directions for CMP. They argue that, new ways and options have emerged due to technological change in the global environment; that it is the role of both organization and individual employees to manage careers. Employees' needed to restructure their old ways of pursuing career (Upward mobility) to new ways (Multi-directional). Chen, Chang and Yeh (2004) argue that the advantage of the new way was, individual employee would be in charge of their own careers since the globe has multiple options and choices they can make. Baruch (2006) viewed the global change in CMP in the twenty-first century was due to technological change. Added that, careers were thought to evolve within the context of one organization, with a linear progression, and success was defined by employee promotion and increase in salary. But with the global changes, the contract has altered, where employees' exchange performance for continual learning and development of their careers to attain job satisfaction

VIII. Job Satisfaction

The concept of job satisfaction emerged from the Hawthorne studies, in the late 1920s and early 1930s by Elton Mayo at the Hawthorne plant of the Western Electric Company in Chicago. Elton Mayo had tremendous influence in the development of HRM to foster social relationships, working conditions, welfare and compensations in the work place. His emphasis was on employee motivation in enhancing productivity. Since then different authors have different approaches towards the definition of job satisfaction (Dysvik&Kuvaas, 2013). Danica (2013) states that, affective job satisfaction and cognitive job satisfaction are the two types of job satisfaction that can determine how well an employee fits with either the job or the organization, The affective job satisfaction (emotional feeling on the job) which includes; the nature of the work, pay/salary, relationship with both employee and supervisor. Sharma and Kaur (2014) argue that, these are intrinsic factors that causes a feeling of dissatisfaction when they are absent and cognitive job satisfaction (belief to be satisfied with particular facets of the job) includes, achievements, employee empowerment and career growth, which are extrinsic.

According to Gupter and Pannu (2013), job satisfaction is an attitudinal behaviour on various aspects of the job that cause satisfaction (motivators) and factors that cause dissatisfaction (hygiene factors). Others describes it as being an emotional response that results from the employees' perceived fulfillment of their needs and what they believe the organization have offered (Alshitri, 2013). The concept of job satisfaction has continued to be of great concern, expanded and unfolded through decades. Majority fine it to be in terms of work-related and social affective reaction (Shelton, 2001; Silverthorne, 2004; Lumley, Coetzee, Tladinyane& Ferreira, 2011 &Wageeh, 2014). Therefore job satisfaction can be viewed as an affective reaction on job aspect, arising from what an employee seek in a job in comparison with the actual outcomes that the job provide to that employee. In United Arab Emirates (UAE) for example, is an oil-producing and wealthy country. Yousef (2009) stated that UAE lack skilled national personnel. Further states that UAE relies almost entirely on expatriate workforce from all over the world. The study found an estimate of about 70 percent of its population is expatriate workers. Found that job position in UAE has generated a multicultural environment and workforce-diverse. The workforce-diverse come with many work challenge and management especially the management of job satisfaction with various job facets for such diverse workforces. Shahzad, Mumtaz, Hayat and Khan (2010) argue that, if the expatriates are satisfied with their workload, pay, supervision co-worker and other work-related issues, they will work hard to accomplish organizational goal and achieve their job satisfaction.

Saari and Judge (2004) assert that the feeling of job satisfaction among employees is an indicator of organizational effectiveness, and it is influenced by both the organizational and personal factors. Majority of employers realize that the optimal functioning of their organization depends in part on the level of employees' job satisfaction, hence the emergence of the statement; happy employees are always productive workers (Donohue & Heywood, 2004). In a normal circumstance, optimal performance needs employee's full potential in all level of organizations, at the same time

organization emphasizes the importance of employee job satisfaction (Morrison, 2008). Job satisfaction therefore, is a result of employee’s perception and the evaluation of their own unique needs, values and expectations, which they regard as being important to them (Ssesanga, 2005). Some of the aspects are pay, promotion, nature of work, relationship with supervision, benefits, relationship with co-worker, contingent rewards, operating procedures and communication.

IX. The Mediating Role of Job Security on Career Management Practices and Job Satisfaction

Job security is one of the mechanism that intervenes the relationship between CMP and employee job satisfaction (Artz& Kaya, 2015 &Bindra, 2014). The long term of a career is an assurance of one’s job security. Improved job security win employees heart and retention will only happen in an institution that learn to master CMP (Maree, 2018). Janes (2018) argued that job satisfaction do not directly shapes the employee’s commitment and performance, while Oluwayemi and Olanyi (2018) stated that, their exist a generative mechanism that explain how the HR functions are able to influence job satisfaction. Meaning that career management practices generates some reactive mechanisms that may influence employees personality traits and behavioural satisfaction (job security), which in turn affect their job satisfaction.

X. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study adopted correlational research design. The study was conducted in chartered public universities in Kenya. The target population comprised 2,355 administrative staff in chartered public universities in Kenya. Purposive sampling technique was used to select ten (10) fully-fledged chartered public universities. Proportionate random sampling technique was used to select 370 administrative staff. Data was collected using three questionnaires, namely; University Administrative Staff Questionnaires (UASQ). Validity were checked and critique by supervisors and research experts in the department of Business Administration Egerton University to ascertain whether items measures what it was supposed to measure. Reliability of instruments was estimated using Cronbach’s Alpha Coefficient for internal consistency. Reliability coefficient of 0.944 was yielded.

XI. DATA ANALYSIS

The data collected were edited, and coded for analysis with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) version 24, computer programme for windows. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the profile of respondents and study variables. Multiple regression was used to test hypotheses at a significance level of alpha (α) equal to 0.05. The null hypotheses were accepted, if $p \geq 0.05$ and rejected if $p < 0.05$ based on results.

XII. RESULTS

The hypothesis states that, job security has no statistically significant effect on career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction in chartered public universities in Kenya. Hierarchical regression analysis was used following Baron and Kenny (1986) four steps approach.

In the first step, simple regression analysis was performed; the (dependent variable) administrative staff job satisfaction was regressed on (independent variable) career management practices. This step examines the significance of the relationship between career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction. Table 1 present results of the analysis.

Table 1: Regression for Career Management Practices and Administrative Staff Job Satisfaction

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.609 ^a	.371	.369	.3310		
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	21.915	1	21.915	200.004	.000 ^b
	Residual	37.145	339	.110		
	Total	59.061	340			

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	1.730	.172		10.077	.000	1.393	2.068
Career management practices	.617	.044	.609	14.142	.000	.531	.703

- a. Predictors: (Constant), career management practices
- b. Dependent Variable: administrative staff Job Satisfaction

Results in table 1 show three models. The first model indicates the coefficient of determination (R^2) of .371, depicts that 37.1% of the variance in administrative staff job satisfaction (dependent variable) was explained by variations in career management practices (independent variable). The second model show F statistics ($F_{2,338}=107,622, p < 0.05$) which means that the model was significant. The third model show the standardized coefficients ($\beta = .609, t = 14.142, p < 0.05$) show the relationship between career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction is positive and significant. The results fulfill the requirement for the first step in the mediating analysis.

The second step of the simple regression analysis, the mediating variable (job security) was regressed on career management practices. The aim of this step examines the significance of the relationship between career management practices (independent variable) and the mediator (job security). Table 2 present results of the analysis.

Table 2: Regression for Career Management Practices and Job Security

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate			
1	.507 ^a	.257	.255	.4065			

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	19.359	1	19.359	117.156	.000 ^b
	Residual	56.018	339	.165		
	Total	75.378	340			

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1 (Constant)	1.888	.211		8.952	.000	1.473	2.302
Career management practices	.580	.054	.507	10.824	.000	.474	.685

- a. Predictors: (Constant), career management practices
- b. Dependent Variable: Job Security

Results in table 2 show three models. The first model indicates the coefficient of determination (R^2) of .257, depicts that 25.7% of the variance in job security (dependent variable) was explained by variations in career management practices (independent variable). The second model show F statistics ($F_{1,339}=117.156, p < 0.05$) which means that the model was significant. The standardized coefficients of ($\beta = .507, t = 10.824, p < 0.05$) show the relationship between career

management practices and job security is positive and significant. The results fulfill the requirement for the second step in the mediating analysis.

The third step of the simple regression analysis, the dependent variable (administrative staff job satisfaction) was regressed on the mediating variable (job security). This step intend to examine the relationship between the mediating variable (job security) and dependent variable (administrative staff job satisfaction). Table 3 present results of the analysis.

Table 3: Regression for Job Security and Administrative Job Satisfaction

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate			
1	.615 ^a	.379	.377	.3290			

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	
1	Regression	22.370	1	22.370	206.682	.000 ^b	
	Residual	36.691	339	.108			
	Total	59.061	340				

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	1.881	.159		11.861	.000	1.569	2.192
	Job Security	.545	.038	.615	14.376	.000	.470	.619

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Security

b, Dependent Variable: Administrative staff Job Satisfaction

Results in table 3 show three models. The first model indicates the coefficient of determination (R²) of .379, depicts that 37.9% of the variance in administrative staff job satisfaction (dependent variable) was explained by variations in job security (independent variable).The second model show F statistics (F_{1,339}=206.682, p < 0.05) which means that the model was significant. The third model indicate the standardized coefficients (β = .615, t = 14.376, p < 0.05) show the relationship between job security and administrative job satisfaction is positive and significant. The results fulfill the requirement for the third step in the mediating analysis.

Step one, two and three confirms the significance of the coefficients between career management practices, job security and administrative job satisfaction. Baron and Kenny (1986) stated that should any one of the above condition not been fulfilled, then there exists no mediator. Therefore, in the fourth step hierarchical regression analysis was performed to examine the effect of X (career management practices) on Y (administrative job satisfaction), while controlling for M (job security). The dependent variable (administrative staff job satisfaction) was regressed on independent variable (career management practices) and the potential mediator (job security) entered in the model as a control variable. The effect between the dependent variable and independent variable was assessed after the effect of mediating variable was controlled for. The aim of this step examines the significant effect of the mediator. Table 4 present results of the analysis.

Table 4: Hierarchical Regression for Effect of Job Security on Career Management Practices and Administrative Job Satisfaction

Model Summary

		Change Statistics											
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change				
1	.609 ^a	.371	.369	.3310	.371	200.004	1	339	.000				
2	.705 ^b	.498	.495	.2963	.127	85.179	1	338	.000				
Model	Sum of Squares		Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.							
1	Regression	21.915	1	21.915	200.004	.000 ^b							
	Residual	37.145	339	.110									
	Total	59.061	340										
2	Regression	29.392	2	14.696	167.423	.000 ^c							
	Residual	29.669	338	.088									
	Total	59.061	340										
Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized T Coefficients	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations		Collinearity Statistics				
	B	Std. Error	Beta		Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Part	Toleranc e	VIF		
1	(Constant)	1.730	.172	10.077	.000	1.393	2.068						
	Career management practices	.617	.044	.609	14.142	.000	.531	.703	.609	.609	.609	1.000	1.000
2	(Constant)	1.041	.171	6.090	.000	.705	1.377						
	Career management practices	.405	.045	.400	8.944	.000	.316	.494	.609	.437	.345	.743	1.346
	Job Security	.365	.040	.413	9.229	.000	.287	.443	.615	.449	.356	.743	1.346

- a. Dependent Variable: Administrative Staff Job Satisfaction
- b. Predictors: (Constant), career management practices
- c. Predictors: (Constant), career management practices, Job Security

Results in table 4 show three models. The first model indicate the coefficient of determination (R²) of .371, depicts that 37.1% of the variance in administrative staff job satisfaction (dependent variable) is explained by variations in career management practices (independent variable). The model also show that, with the addition of job security into the model, explained 12.7% (R² change = .127) variation in administrative staff job satisfaction and the (F change = 85.179, p < 0.05) is significant. The second model show F statistics (F_{1,339}=200.004, p < 0.05) which means that the model was significant, and the additional variance in administrative staff job satisfaction is still significant (F_{2,338}=167.423, p < 0.05). The third model indicate the standardized coefficients (β = .609, t = 14.142, p < 0.05) show the effect of career management practices on administrative staff job satisfaction is positive and significant. The model further indicates standardized coefficients (β = .413, t = 9.229, p < 0.05) shows the effect of job security on administrative staff job

satisfaction is positive and significant. Lastly, the model show when job security was controlled for, the standardized coefficients reduce but still significant ($\beta = .413$, $t = 9.229$, $p < 0.05$). However, the results shows that the effect of career management practices on administrative staff job satisfaction reduced ($\beta = .400$) as compared with the step one ($\beta = .609$). Demonstrate that job security partially mediate the relationship between career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction. Because the β value decreased but still remained positive and significant. The final condition for mediation was met. Thus, the null hypothesis (H_{06}) that job security has no statistically significant effect on career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction in chartered public universities in Kenya is rejected. The results of the study show that job security partially mediate the effect of career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction in chartered public universities in Kenya.

XIII. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Hierarchical regression analysis was employed to establish the mediating effect of job security on career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction using the four steps suggested by Baron and Kenny (1986). The purpose was to establish whether job security mediates the relationship between career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction.

The results of this study showed that job security partially mediate the relationship between career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction. Implies that to some extent, there is no total direct relationship between career management practices and administrative staffs job satisfaction. Career management practices first influences job security, which in turn exert a positive impact on administrative job satisfaction, hence casual chain of effect. Results indicated controlling for job security, the beta value between career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction decreases. The amount of decreased value had direct relation with job security. Suggesting that the relationship between career management practices and administrative staffs job satisfaction can be realized through the improvement of job security.

These findings provide insight understanding, when institutions provide career management practices (career needs, career planning initiatives, career development programmes and career path progression) employees place higher value on job security, which will then affect job satisfaction. This means administrative staff exposed to career management practices tend to acquire job security in their career would probably feel more satisfied.

These findings are in agreement with Alusa and Karuiki (2015) study on HR practices and employees outcome. The study found a positive and significant correlation between HR practices and employees outcome, the study further found that, the effects of structural change in organizations and global competition have contributed universality approaches commonly referred to as best practices. Which includes, teamwork, job rotation, empowerment, skill development and many others demand institutions to adopt to improve employee job security and job satisfaction. Imocho, Nzulwa and Kwena (2017) in their study found that, different management practices such as career development, career planning and career path have positive relationship with job security and job satisfaction.

The findings of this study indicates that 61.5% change in administrative staff job satisfaction are attributed to job security, an indication that job security can offer an array of benefits including employee commitment, retention and staff performance. Kamendat and Didona (2016) argued that employees who perceive to have knowledge and skills are likely to express increased job security and job satisfaction. In addition, the findings indicates that job security partial mediate career management and administrative staff job satisfaction. These findings support other related prior studies such as Sagwa, Obonyo and Ogutu (2015) who found that job security partially mediates the relationship between HR practices perception and intention to remain in the organization. They argued that understanding this relationship in public listed institutions in developing world is equally important for employment security. Mutua (2017) noted that employees do not bring this key issue of work attitudes and behaviors on entry into any institution but they acquire them in the workplace, through a process of key developmental career management practices, they exhibit and reinforce them in decision-making process. These findings are in consistent with Nyambura and Kamara (2017) who stated that, the process of civilizing employees' skills and knowledge in institutions, the more they exert effort in their assigned tasks the more they pursue the organization's interests.

Therefore, the study findings reveal that employees job security in chartered public universities partially address job satisfaction and job anxiety of looking for more secure employment. However, understanding how employees evaluate their job security is an important step to explain the mechanism through which career management practices influence job satisfaction. The partial mediation demonstrates that in addition to indirect influence, there exists direct influence. In sum, the findings are important for HR managers to implement career management practices that allow employees to

feel more secure as shown to have more value by majority of administrative staff. Maree (2018) argued that organizations that provide higher degree of job security convey a clear message that the organization has a longstanding commitment to its workforce. A Meta-analysis on cognitive/affective distinction of job insecurity study in Belgium North-West University found that academic staff job insecurity negatively relate to work outcome such as job satisfaction.

CONCLUSION

Job security affects both career management practices and administrative staff job satisfaction. Chartered public universities need to pay attention to HR functions that ensures job security.

ECOMMENDATION

Job security is crucial in enhancing administrative staff job satisfaction. More effort is needed to integrate job security measures within human resource functions to enhance job satisfaction.

SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The study focused on administrative staff; however, replicated study can be conduct in private universities in Kenya. This will enhance understanding on job security, career management practices and job satisfaction, for comparison and generalization of results.

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